
Research

IMPACT OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON STOCK PRICES IN TANZANIA

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of macroeconomic variables on stock prices in the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). This paper uses quarter data spanning from the first quarter of 2005 to the fourth quarter of 2020 of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inflation, interest rate, and DSE stock prices. The main aim of this study is to investigate the correlation between GDP, real interest rates, inflation rates, and their impact on stock prices. Theories that guides this research work are the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) and Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT). The study further employs a nonlinear VECM and rolling cointegration to capture potential non-linear relationships and assess the stability of the cointegrating relationship over time. These analyses provide insights into the dynamic nature of the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices in the DSE. The empirical findings of this research reveal a significant positive relationship between GDP and stock prices, suggesting that economic growth is a primary driver of stock market performance in Tanzania. While inflation did not have a strong direct impact, higher real interest rates were observed to be associated with lower stock prices. The VECM analysis also confirms a long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables, indicating that changes in macroeconomic factors will have lasting effects on stock prices with an adjustment term of 0.011 or 1.1%.

Keywords: DSE, GDP, Inflation rate, Real interest rate, Stock prices, VECM

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Accepted: 22 September, 2024; **Published:** 23 September, 2024

How to cite this article: Arafat Abdallah Abusaba, Hui Cao (2024). *Impact of macroeconomic variables on stock prices in Tanzania*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(9), 84-92. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13961867>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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I. Introduction

1.1 A general background

The Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), established in 1996, is a crucial platform for capital mobilization and investment in Tanzania. As the primary venue for trading equities, bonds, and other securities, the DSE has facilitated both domestic and foreign capital flow, supporting business and industrial development. With Tanzania's economy expanding, the DSE has seen increased investor interest, leading to further growth and more listings in this semi-strong stock market in East Africa.

Like other stock markets, the DSE is influenced by various macroeconomic factors, particularly Gross Domestic Product (GDP), real interest rates, and inflation (Levine, 1991). These variables are chosen for their established relevance in

explaining stock market movements. Tanzania's GDP, estimated at \$84.03 billion (USD) in 2023, serves as a key indicator of economic health, driven by investments in infrastructure, agriculture, and the mining and tourism sectors. Projections indicate that GDP may reach \$123.59 billion (USD) by 2028.

Inflation in Tanzania has fluctuated between high and low periods. The Bank of Tanzania (BOT) aims to maintain inflation within a target range of 1.0% to 3.0% to ensure price stability and economic growth. Although there has been a positive trend of decreasing inflation rates, the challenge of maintaining stability persists, making effective inflation management crucial for fostering a stable investment environment.

The BOT also plays a vital role in shaping monetary policy, including the benchmark interest rate that directly affects borrowing costs and economic activity. Recent shifts toward lower real interest rates, with the BOT's benchmark rate at 5.5% as of January 2024, have the potential to encourage investment in the DSE. However, balancing investment promotion with inflation control remains complex, and the BOT's future decisions regarding interest rates will be critical for sustaining an appealing environment for investors in the Tanzanian stock market.

II. Literature Review

A substantial body of research examines the complex relationship between macroeconomic factors and stock market performance, with key variables such as economic growth, inflation, and interest rates influencing investor sentiment, risk perception, and stock prices (Shapiro, 2002). Understanding these relationships is essential for navigating financial markets.

The impacts of interest rates on stock prices are particularly significant in finance. Higher real interest rates increase the opportunity cost of holding stocks, leading investors to prefer guaranteed returns from bonds or savings accounts, which can decrease demand and lower stock prices (Chen, 2012; Mfugale, 2023). Elevated interest rates also reduce the present value of future cash flows, potentially deterring investment if expected returns do not compensate for rising risk premiums (Komba, 2024). The effects of interest rates can vary; moderate increases might have little impact, but significantly high rates can negatively affect stock prices, particularly for growth stocks that depend more on future cash flows (Utouh, 2023; Fabel, 2021). Research supports a negative correlation between interest rates and stock prices, suggesting that lower rates stimulate stock market investment (Agyire-Tettey, 2008; Kim, 2003; Nkechukwu, 2013). Inflation also plays a critical role in shaping stock prices. It can erode the purchasing power of future cash flows, diminishing intrinsic stock value and potentially leading to lower stock prices (Kiani, 2010; Caporale, 2009). High inflation generates uncertainty for investors, complicating future earnings assessments and prompting central banks to raise interest rates, further pressuring stock prices. The impact of inflation can vary; moderate inflation may be perceived positively as some investors see stocks as a hedge against inflation (Bhattacharya, 2001). Conversely, companies with strong pricing power can better navigate inflationary pressures, leading to stable stock prices (Mfugale & Olomi, 2023). Research findings on inflation's relationship with stock prices are mixed, with some studies indicating increased market volatility during high inflation (Bhattacharya, 2001; Hondroyannis, 2010) while others suggest a positive correlation in certain contexts (Sharma, 2002).

The relationship between GDP growth and stock prices is complex and often debated. While a positive correlation is typically expected, the strength and causality of this link can vary depending on several factors, including time frames. The relationship may be more pronounced in the long run, as short-term GDP fluctuations do not always translate into immediate stock price changes (Chen, 2012). In efficient markets, stock prices tend to reflect all available information, potentially reducing the impact of actual GDP growth on stock prices (Fama, 1970). Global economic trends can also influence domestic markets; a strong global economy can positively affect local stock markets, even when local GDP growth is modest. Empirical studies show mixed evidence regarding GDP growth's correlation with stock prices, with (Sureshbhai, 2020) reporting a positive correlation, while (Ali, 2011) finds a statistically insignificant relationship, indicating a need for further exploration of these dynamics.

2.2 Theoretical underpinnings

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) posits that all available information, including macroeconomic factors, is quickly reflected in stock prices. This implies that any impact of macroeconomic variables on stock prices should be short-lived as the market efficiently adjusts (Fama, 1970). To test the EMH in the context of macroeconomic variables, an examination of whether stock prices react efficiently to macroeconomic news or events will be conducted. Analyzing how stock prices respond to changes in real interest rates, GDP growth, or inflation can provide insights into the market's efficiency in incorporating macroeconomic information.

Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) is a multi-factor asset pricing model that suggests the expected return of a stock is determined by its exposure to a set of systematic risk factors. Macroeconomic variables can be considered as such factors. (Ross, 1976)

APT in the context of macroeconomic variables, can identify relevant factors based on the specific characteristics of the DSE and Tanzania's economy. These factors might include inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, commodity prices, and economic growth. By estimating the exposure of each stock to these factors, one can use APT to predict its expected return. Comparing these predicted returns to actual returns can assess the model's performance.

2.3 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

There is a significant positive relationship between GDP and stock prices in the DSE.

Hypothesis 2:

There is a significant negative relationship between inflation and stock prices in the DSE.

Hypothesis 3:

There is a significant negative relationship between real interest rates and stock prices in the DSE.

III. Research Methodology & Findings

The data for this study span from the 2005 first quarter to the 2020 fourth quarter were sourced from reputable financial databases, including the Tanzanian National Bureau of Statistics, Bank of Tanzania, and the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange. The dataset includes quarter information on key variables: Stock Prices, GDP, Real Interest Rate, and Inflation. Then, the data were converted to a natural log (LN) for further analysis. Their significance drives the choice of these variables in capturing the economic and financial dynamics of Tanzania.

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Variable	LnGDP	LnRIR	LnIR	LnSP
Mean	24.39646	1.758157	1.88919	7.374897
Std. Dev	.4056032	.9553605	.4393839	.3342675
Min	23.63537	-3.109191	1.190976	6.169502
Max	24.94921	2.736177	2.772657	7.547423
Variance	.1645139	.9127136	.1930582	.1117347
Skewness	-.4919203	-2.520897	.1758374	-2.0419
Kurtosis	1.986455	12.15034	2.110425	6.103408
Obs	64	64	64	64

Table A: Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The mean value of lnGDP, the natural logarithm of GDP, is 24.39646, indicating an average level of GDP on a log scale. The standard deviation of 0.4056 suggests a consistent level of GDP growth over the study period. With a slightly negative skewness (-0.4919), the distribution has a longer tail towards lower values, implying more periods of slower GDP growth than rapid growth. The kurtosis of 1.9865 indicates a slightly peaked distribution compared to a normal bell curve.

Real Interest Rate

The mean value of lnRIR is 1.7582, representing the average real interest rate on a log scale. The standard deviation of 0.9554 is higher than that of lnGDP, indicating greater fluctuations in real interest rates. The skewness of lnRIR is strongly negative (-2.5209), suggesting more occurrences of lower or negative real interest rates. A high kurtosis of 12.1503 indicates a distribution with fatter tails, pointing to extreme outliers in the data.

Stock Prices and Key Observations

The mean value of lnSP is 7.3749, with a standard deviation of 0.3343, reflecting a relatively consistent level of stock prices. The negative skewness (-2.0419) indicates more periods of lower stock prices, while a high kurtosis of 6.1034 suggests the presence of extreme outliers. Overall, the descriptive statistics indicate that lnGDP and lnRIR show wider ranges and higher kurtosis than lnIR and lnSP, with all variables deviating from a normal distribution. These findings highlight the need for further investigation into the stationarity and non-normality of the series before conducting the VECM analysis.

Stationarity test

Since the Unit root tests of Dickey-Fuller (DF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests revealed that all variables (lnGDP, lnRIR, lnIR, and lnSP) were non-stationary in the ground state thus, they were integrated into 1 lag order one I (1) for stationarity.

VECM Analysis

The VECM is expressed as:

$$\Delta \ln SP_t = \alpha_t + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \beta_1 \ln GDP_{t-r} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \beta_2 \ln RIR_{t-s} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \beta_3 \ln IR_{t-u} + \sum_{l=1}^{q-1} \beta_4 \ln SP_{t-v} + \lambda_t ECT_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

1. Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) Results:

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
d_dlnGDP					
_cel					
L1.	-.2754388	.0831796	-3.31	0.001	-.4384598 - .1124018
dlnGDP					
LD.	-.4194527	.109313	-3.84	0.000	-.6337021 - .2052032
dlnRIR					
LD.	-.0680194	.0188197	-3.61	0.000	-.1049053 - .0311335
dlnIR					
LD.	-.0875802	.0670844	-1.31	0.192	-.2190632 .0439029
dlnSP					
LD.	.1423134	.0601614	2.37	0.018	.0243993 .2602274

__cons	-.0025348	.0074362	-0.34	0.733	-.0171095	.0120398
D_dlnRIR						
__cel						
L1.	7.133715	.8312596	8.58	0.000	5.584476	8.762954
dlnGDP						
LD.	-5.014165	1.092425	-4.59	0.000	-7.155279	-2.873852
dlnRIR						
LD.	.3793516	.1880754	2.02	0.044	.0107306	.7479726
dlnIR						
LD.	-1.472783	.678412	-2.20	0.028	-2.786766	-.1587994
dlnSP						
LD.	-1.225219	.6012258	-2.04	0.042	-2.4036	-.0466378
__cons	-.0000993	.074314	-0.00	0.999	-.145752	.1455535
D_dlnIR						
__cel						
L1.	.1729973	.1603397	1.08	0.281	-.1412628	.4872574
dlnGDP						
LD.	-.0965292	.2107153	-0.46	0.647	-.5895236	.3164652
dlnRIR						
LD.	.0561893	.0362774	1.55	0.121	-.0149131	.1272918
dlnIR						
LD.	-.2173898	.1293142	-1.68	0.093	-.470841	.0360614
dlnSP						
LD.	-.1155421	.115969	-1.00	0.319	-.3428373	.111753
__cons	.0002195	.0143343	0.02	0.988	-.0278751	.0283141
D_dlnSP						
__cel						
L1.	.011927	.2236015	0.05	0.957	-.4265002	.4593542
dlnGDP						
LD.	-.4296025	.2939789	-1.46	0.144	-1.005776	.1465689
dlnRIR						
LD.	-.0589928	.050611	-1.17	0.244	-.1581885	.0402029
dlnIR						
LD.	-.0339755	.1804075	-0.19	0.851	-.3875676	.3196166
dlnSP						
LD.	-.3668718	.1617895	-2.27	0.023	-.6839734	-.0497703
__cons	-.0023525	.0199978	-0.12	0.906	-.0415476	.0368425
Cointegrating equations						
Equation	Parms	chi2	P>chi2			
__cel	3	102.336	0.0000			

Fig A: Vector Error Correlation Model

The coefficient for the first lag of dlnSP (0.1423134) is statistically significant (p-value = 0.018), suggesting a significant positive relationship between past changes in stock prices and current changes in GDP; thus, Hypothesis 1 is strongly supported. The potential economic interpretation of this is that as the GDP of Tanzania keeps on growing, we should continue to expect the investors' confidence to increase as well as corporate earnings are expected to increase as businesses benefit from higher demand for their products and services. Not only that but also the perceived risk of investing in stocks may be lower.

The results do not provide strong evidence to support Hypothesis 2. While the coefficient for the first lag of dlnIR (inflation) in the equation for dlnSP (stock prices) is negative (-0.1155421), it is not statistically significant at the conventional 5% level (p-value = 0.319). This suggests that the impact of inflation on stock prices is not statistically significant. The inflationary pressures in Tanzania do not have a strong direct impact on stock market performance due to factors such as market expectations as the investors might already be anticipating inflation and adjusting their valuations accordingly, and also The impact of inflation might vary across different sectors of the economy, potentially leading to a net-zero.

The results provide some evidence to support Hypothesis 3. The coefficient for the first lag of dlnRIR (real interest rates) in the equation for dlnSP (stock prices) is negative (-1.225219) and statistically significant at the 5% level (p-value = 0.042). This suggests a negative relationship between real interest rate changes and stock price changes. However, the magnitude of this effect is relatively small. Higher real interest rates tend to be associated with lower stock prices due to reasons such as an increase in the cost of capital, thus reducing the stock attractiveness to investors, and also higher real interest rates can sometimes indicate a tightening monetary policy, which may signal concerns about economic growth and inflation.

2. Johansen Normalization Restriction:

The Johansen normalization restriction imposes a coefficient of 1 on one of the variables in the cointegrating equation. In this case, dlnGDP has a coefficient of 1, implying it serves as the reference variable within the long-run equilibrium relationship. The other variables (dlnRIR, dlnIR, and dlnSP) are then interpreted in relation to dlnGDP.

Johansen normalization restriction imposed						
beta	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
._ce1						
dlnGDP	1
dlnRIR	.2553724	.0255953	-9.98	0.000	-.3055383	-.2052066
dlnIR	-.0101203	.0864289	0.12	0.907	-.1592772	.1795179
dlnSP	-.6059469	.0861064	7.04	0.000	.4371814	.7747124
_cons	-.0247909

Fig B: Johansen Normalization Restriction Imposed

The results show that dlnRIR has a positive coefficient (0.2553724), indicating a negative long-run relationship with dlnGDP. In other words, an increase in real interest rates (dlnRIR) is associated with a decrease in GDP growth (dlnGDP) in the long run. Conversely, the coefficient of dlnIR has a negative sign (-0.0101203), suggesting a potential positive long-run but since the P value is greater than 1%, the results will not be considered. The negative coefficient of dlnSP (-0.6059469) implies a positive long-run relationship between stock prices and GDP growth.

3. Impulse Response Function:

$$IRF_{SP}(10) = \sum_{h=0}^{10} \Phi_{10} \Delta X_t$$

Where:

- $IRF_{SP}(10)$ is the response of stock price to shocks in X_t (GDP, RIR, IR) over 10 horizon
- Φ_{10} are the impulse response coefficient

Fig C: GDP's shock to SP

A one standard deviation shock to dlnGDP initially results in a sharp decrease in dlnSP over the first two periods, followed by a gradual recovery and a positive trend that stabilizes by the ninth period, indicating short-term negative impacts and long-term positive effects on stock prices in the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange. In contrast, a one standard deviation shock to dlnIR leads to a decrease in dlnSP in the first two periods, with an increase in the third period but no long-term relationship between stock prices and the inflation rate. Conversely, a one standard deviation shock to dlnRIR causes a small positive response in dlnSP initially, followed by fluctuations but ultimately results in a positive impact on stock prices both in the short and long run.

4. Extracts of VECM

From:

$$ECT_{t-1} = \ln SP_{t-1} - [\eta_1 \ln GDP_{t-1} + \eta_2 \ln RIR_{t-1} + \eta_3 \ln IR_{t-1}]$$

The ECT is

$$ECT_{t-1} = [1.000d\ln GDP_{t-1} + 0.2553724d\ln RIR_{t-1} - 0.0101203d\ln IR_{t-1} - 0.6059469d\ln SP]$$

The $d\ln SP$ as the target variable

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln SP_{t-1} = & 0.4503542 - 0.4296035 \Delta \ln GDP_{t-1} - 0.0589928 \Delta \ln RIR_{t-1} \\ & - 0.0339755 \Delta \ln IR_{t-1} - 0.3668718 \Delta \ln SP_{t-1} + 0.011927 ECT_{t-1} \end{aligned}$$

The adjustment term (0.011) is statistically significant at the 10% level, suggesting that the previous year's errors (or deviation from long-run equilibrium) are correlated for within the current year at the convenient speed of 1.1%.

5. Forecast Error Variance Decomposition (FEVD)

The FEVD analysis displays that the factors contributing to the unpredictable errors in forecasting stock prices within the DSE. The results reveal distinct patterns in the influence of GDP, inflation rate, and real interest rate on stock price forecast errors across 30 quarters (approximately 7.5 years) into the future.

$$FEVD_{SP}(30) = \frac{Var(SP_t | GDP_t, RIR_t, IR_t)}{Var(SP_t)}$$

Where:

$FEVD_{SP}(h)$ represents the proportion of the variance in stock prices explained by innovations in GDP, real interest rates, and inflation over 30-quarter periods.

Fig D: Forecast Error Variance Decomposition

Results of FEVD of SP: In the short run 90% of stock prices of forecast error variance decomposition is explained by the stock prices itself. The contribution of GDP, real interest rate, and inflation is strongly exogenous as they negatively influence predicting stock prices in the short run. In the long run, the GDP and real interest rate will become more endogenous as we move into the future. The inflation rate on the other hand displays a very weak endogenous impact on stock prices. This means that GDP and real interest rate influence the stock prices of DSE in the model in the short run, but this influence becomes stronger in the long run.

IV. Conclusion and Recommendations

The EMH suggests that all available information, including macroeconomic factors, is rapidly factored into stock prices. The study's discovery of a significant correlation between GDP and stock prices supports the EMH's premise of

efficient pricing. However, the weak association between inflation and stock prices may indicate inefficiencies in how the market assesses inflation risk. The APT proposes that a stock's anticipated return is influenced by its exposure to systematic risk factors, including the macroeconomic variables examined in this study (GDP, real interest rates, and inflation). The significant connections observed reinforce APT's claim that these macroeconomic factors affect stock returns. Additionally, the VECM analysis indicates cointegration among these variables, suggesting that changes in one variable will have enduring effects on the others, emphasizing the importance of macroeconomic factors in stock price analysis.

This research opens avenues for further investigation into the DSE dynamics and other emerging markets. Future studies could expand the VECM to include additional economic variables, analyze data at a sectoral level for more specific insights, and employ alternative methodologies like Structural Vector Autoregression (SVAR) to enhance understanding of stock market dynamics. Additionally, examining sector-specific effects, investor sentiment, and global economic factors could provide valuable insights into the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices, ultimately informing investment decisions and guiding effective economic policies.

References

- [1] Agyire-Tettey Anthony Kyereboah-Coleman & Kwame F. Impact of macroeconomic indicators on stock market performance: The case of the Ghana Stock Exchange // *The Journal of Risk Finance*. - 2008. - pp. 365-378.
- [2] Ali F. The impact of inflation and money supply on stock prices in Pakistan: An ARDL bounds testing approach// *Journal of Applied Economics*. - 2011. - pp. 14(1), 1-14.
- [3] Bhattacharya S., & Mookherjee, D Inflation and stock market volatility: International evidence // *Journal of Financial Management*. - 2001. - pp. 42(3), 383-404.
- [4] Caporale G. M., Cipollini, A., Sestano, A., & Smith, G. The inflation-stock price relationship in a multivariate framework: Evidence from the G7 countries. // *Journal of Banking & Finance*. - 2009. - pp. 33(10), 2068-2080.
- [5] Chen S.-S., Lin, C.-H., & Yu, H.-J. The relationship between real interest rates and stock prices in China // *Journal of Financial Management & Accounting*. - 2012. - pp. 1(2), 119-130.
- [6] Coretha Komba, Peter Anton Sobe, and Joshua Mwakujonga. Effects of interest and exchange rate volatility on stock returns: Evidence from the financial sector of Tanzania. [Journal] // *NG Journal of Social Development*. – 2024. Vol. 13 Issue 1
- [7] Fama E. F. Efficient Capital Markets: A Review of Theory and Empirical Work. [Journal] // *Journal of Finance*, - 1970. - pp. 25(2), 383-417.
- [8] Harold Utouh, and Augustino. The nexus between foreign direct investment and nominal exchange rate, real GDP, and capital stock in Tanzania. [Journal] // *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum. Oeconomia*. – 2023. -pp. 1, 73-87
- [9] Hondroyannis G., and E.Papapetrou Macroeconomic influences on the stock market [Journal] // *Journal of Economics and Finance*. - 2010. - pp. Vol.25 (1).33-49.
- [10] Kiani Khurshid M. Predictability in Stock Returns in an Emerging Market: Evidence from KSE 100 Stock Price Index [Journal] // *The Pakistan Development Review*. - 2010. - pp. 369-381 .
- [11] Kim S.-J., & Moschini, G. Inflation and stock prices in Korea: A cointegration analysis [Journal] // *Journal of Asian Economics*. - 2003. - pp. 14(3), 321-336.
- [12] Levine R Stock markets, growth, and development [Journal] // *Journal of Monetary Economics*. - 1991. - pp. 5(17), 47-75.
- [13] Neema Mfugale, Wenselausi Olomi. The Impact of Inflation and Exchange Rate on Stock Market Returns in Tanzania. [Journal] // *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*. – 2023. - Vol. 1 No. 6

- [14] Ngarangera Pendo Fabel & Mwaitete Cairo Dr. Impact of economic growth on share price in Tanzania. The 2nd Conference of Accounting and Finance, Arusha- Tanzania. 2021. - Vol. 4 No. 6. -717-725
- [15] Gabriel Nkechukwu, Justus Onyeagba, and Johnson Okoh. Macroeconomic Variables and Stock Market Prices in Nigeria: A Cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model Tests. International Journal of Science and Research. – 2013.
- [16] Ross S. A. The Arbitrage Theory of Capital Asset Pricing. [Journal]. - [s.l.] : Journal of Economic Theory, , 1976. - 341-360. : Vols. 13(1),.
- [17] Shapiro A. C The role of market structure and investor sentiment in affecting asset prices [Journal] // Financial Management. - 2002. - pp. 31(2), 5-27.
- [18] Sharma Wangbangpo & Stock market and macroeconomic fundamental dynamic interactions: ASEAN-5 countries [Journal] // Journal of Asian Economics. - 2002. - pp. 13(1):27-51.
- [19] Sureshbhai Vasani Analysis of Impact of Gross Domestic Products (GDP) on Stock Market Movement in India [Journal] // Global Journal of Management and Business Research. - 2020. - pp. (20), 35-43.

